

ADOLESCENT EATING DISORDERS IN A SOUTH ASIAN CONTEXT: PREVALENCE, PREDICTORS, AND PREVENTION

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Abstract: Eating Disorders (ED) represent a rising public health concern, particularly among adolescents, where early onset often leads to chronic medical and psychosocial consequences. Despite the increasing global prevalence of EDs, research in South Asian populations remains limited. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and associated risk factors of ED among adolescents in Mirpur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (AJK), Pakistan.

A cross-sectional study was conducted in August 2023 among 384 high school and college students aged 12–18 years. The sample was selected using convenience sampling, with the sample size determined via the Raosoft calculator. Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire that included the SCOFF screening tool and the Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire (EDE-Q). Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 22, applying Pearson’s Chi-square, Kruskal-Wallis, and Wald tests.

Findings revealed a high overall ED prevalence of 61.5%, with females constituting the majority of those at risk (72% of the sample). Awareness of EDs was low, with 55.5% of participants unfamiliar with the condition. A significant association was found between gender and ED risk ($p < 0.05$), with females being 0.461 times more likely to be at risk. Notably, ED prevalence was higher among adolescents with normal BMI (59.7%), urban residents (69%), illiterate guardians (41.1%), and those from high-income backgrounds (30.5%). Female participants also had significantly higher concerns related to eating and body weight (mean ranks of 198.24 and 196.63, respectively).

The results underscore the need for early identification and targeted awareness campaigns, especially for young females. School-based mental health programs and screening initiatives using validated tools like SCOFF and EDE-Q could facilitate early intervention and help mitigate long-term consequences.

Keywords: Eating Disorders, Adolescents, BMI, Prevalence, Risk Factors

Introduction

Eating Disorders (ED) are severe psychiatric conditions characterized by persistent disturbances in eating behaviors, body image, and weight perception.

These disorders, though historically underreported in non-Western contexts, are gaining recognition as significant public health concerns across the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2021)

identifies EDs as among the most fatal mental illnesses, with an individual succumbing to ED-related complications every 62 minutes. These disorders are typically classified into specific categories such as Anorexia Nervosa (AN), Bulimia Nervosa (BN), Binge Eating Disorder (BED), Avoidant/Restrictive Food Intake Disorder (ARFID), and Other Specified Feeding or Eating Disorders (OSFED), previously referred to as EDNOS (Eating Disorder Not Otherwise Specified).

Adolescence, a critical developmental stage marked by profound physical, emotional, and psychological transformations, is a period of heightened vulnerability to EDs. It is during this phase that individuals, particularly females, experience intensified concerns about appearance, societal expectations, and peer comparisons. This increased sensitivity can lead to disordered eating behaviors ranging from restrictive dieting to compulsive overeating and purging. Jenkins et al. (2014) classified EDs as the third most prevalent chronic condition in adolescents, trailing only obesity and asthma.

The prevalence of EDs is rising globally. According to recent estimates, the global incidence has surged from 3.4% to 7.8% within the past decade. This upward trend is not confined to Western societies but is increasingly being observed in Asian regions, including Pakistan. Yet, data from South Asia remains sparse, and the cultural context complicates recognition and diagnosis. Social taboos, lack of awareness, and the limited mental health infrastructure further hinder effective diagnosis and treatment.

Anorexia Nervosa (AN), characterized by an intense fear of weight gain, distorted body image, and dangerously low body weight, is associated with one of the highest mortality rates among psychiatric illnesses (Golden et al., 2016a). Bulimia Nervosa (BN), meanwhile, is defined by recurrent episodes of binge eating followed by compensatory behaviors such as vomiting, fasting, or excessive exercise. Unlike AN, individuals with BN often maintain a normal or slightly above-average weight, which makes it harder to detect. Binge Eating Disorder (BED), though often overlooked, involves recurrent episodes of uncontrolled eating without subsequent purging, leading to significant emotional distress. ARFID is another classification that presents with selective or avoidant eating, often due to sensory issues or past traumatic experiences associated with food, and results in nutritional deficiencies and impaired physical development.

Psychosocial influences play a pivotal role in the development of EDs. In particular, adolescent girls are disproportionately affected due to increased societal pressure to conform to idealized body images perpetuated by media, peers, and sometimes family members. Teasing related to body size or weight—a common form of bullying—has been associated with low self-esteem and disordered eating behaviors (Philippi & Leme, 2018). In patriarchal societies like Pakistan, where conversations around mental health and body image are often stigmatized, adolescents may internalize these pressures without seeking appropriate help, leading to long-term psychological and physical damage.

Cultural factors further compound the problem. In many South Asian households, food holds a central place in familial and social life. While this can be a source of community and care, it may also result in rigid expectations around eating practices, body types, and gender roles. Girls are often expected to maintain a certain physique to be considered attractive or marriageable, while boys may face pressure to be muscular or fit. These cultural narratives reinforce unhealthy body ideals and may drive adolescents toward extreme dieting or exercise regimes, which are precursors to EDs.

The sociocultural environment in Mirpur (AJK), like much of Pakistan, is characterized by traditional family structures, varying literacy levels, and limited access to psychological services. Adolescents in such settings may experience a mix of modern influences through social media and conservative family expectations, creating cognitive dissonance and identity conflicts. This dual exposure could be a contributing factor to the rise of EDs in areas previously considered low-risk. Unfortunately, most mental health research in Pakistan has focused on depression, anxiety, and substance abuse, leaving a substantial gap in the literature concerning adolescent EDs.

Existing tools such as the SCOFF questionnaire and the Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire (EDE-Q) have proven effective in early screening of EDs. The SCOFF tool is a brief five-question screening instrument that targets core ED symptoms such as loss of control over eating, self-induced vomiting, and significant weight loss. The EDE-Q is a more comprehensive self-report questionnaire that

assesses the frequency and severity of eating-related thoughts and behaviors. Utilizing these validated instruments in school settings can aid in early identification and facilitate timely referrals to mental health professionals.

Despite the gravity of EDs, awareness in Pakistan remains minimal. Healthcare professionals often lack training in recognizing and managing EDs, and community-level educational programs are virtually nonexistent. Schools rarely provide psychological counseling services, and there are few mental health campaigns that address eating behaviors among adolescents. Consequently, most cases go undiagnosed until they result in serious physical complications or psychological breakdowns.

The current study aims to address this gap by assessing the prevalence of EDs among adolescents in Mirpur (AJK), using standardized tools and identifying key sociodemographic risk factors such as gender, body mass index (BMI), residence type, education level, and income group. By highlighting the prevalence and patterns of disordered eating in a relatively under-researched area, this research contributes to the growing need for context-specific public health interventions.

Psychiatric illnesses associated with eating disorders include low self-esteem, depression, personality issue, failure to manage emotions and worthlessness. Eating disorder has impact on people of all ages and genders. Binge eating and BN has high ratio of mortality and morbidity. Women have 3 times more chances to suffer bulimia and anorexia. A prevalence rate of 21.7 % of anorexia found in nursing and medical students in Karachi. Disturbed eating

behavior has many risk factors including media , friends , self - esteem and diligence .these disorderly eating attitudes are due to adaptation of western culture and dissatisfied unrealistic body shape perception which leads to depression . (Bibi, 2014).

Depression is related to mental disorders that severely effect individual's functioning capability and due depression society has facing economic costs, because the victim fails to perform social and occupational function due to the result of depression symptoms, which include insomnia, irritability, confusion, depressed mood. When people are depressed, they eat more and more than their requirements, which may be due to overcome these negative thoughts and depression, through which they are suffering. Depression elevates chances and danger of eating disorders and highly linked with obesity. Association of eating disorders and depression has more frequency in females as compared to males.(Saleem et al., 2014). Athletes has high risk of disordered eating because ideal body condition is required in sports, pressure from coaches, parents and other competent provoke to lose weight, dieting, frequent weight cycling, severe training, injuries have impact on athletes eating disorders. Eating disorders are more prevalent among athletes than in general population. Anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, binge eating disorder, other feeding disorders has 8% chances in global population. eating disorders are chronic, and have high relapse rate. It can be transmitted by genes heritability. Estimation shows a genetic transmission of anorexia nervosa (58 -74%), bulimia nervosa (59% - 83%), binge eating disorder (41 % - 57 %). It shows sizable percentage of trait variance, so called single – nucleotide

polymorphism-based heritability. The United Kingdom eating disorders genetics initiative (EDGI) has objective to increase our comprehension of eating disorders by gathering genetic and phenotypic data from at least 10,000 people and linking it with their medical history. Environmental and psychological factors a role in the etiology of eating disorders. Environmental factor: include premature birth, traumatic experiences and social media use. Psychological factor has increased its risk such as body satisfaction and loss of self-esteem. But positive relationship with parents and siblings including regular meals times, not bullying about weight and body appreciation can be a barrier against eating disorders. (Monssen et al., 2024).

After COVID -19 pandemic many changes occur in people life such as isolated behavior, enhanced media exposure, disrupted routine activities, and exaggeration of disordered eating disorders. People were suffering from worsening of symptoms including dietary restraint. Dietary restraint may be maladaptive way to balance negative body related self – conscious emotions which can be embarrassment, like shame and guilt of being overweight. Some people use unhealthy food in this regard like protein shakes, laxatives, weight loss medicines and drinks which can worsen their condition. (Bourke and Pila, 2023).

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The Cross-sectional study was conducted on 384 adult girls and boys, sample size calculated by using Raosoft calculator, according to the recent census the total population of the Mirpur AJK was 456200. Data was collected by convenience sampling technique

from the students of different high schools and colleges in 2023. Participant of age 12-18 years were allowed to participate and those who were not previously diagnosed with an eating disorder. At the start of the research, school teachers were asked to explain forms and study to the students so that they will be able to answer the questions correctly, because no translated version was used. Risk factors of ED were analyzed by SCOFF (Sick, Control, One, Fat, Food) was designed for diagnosis of AN and BN, and EDE-Q (Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire). EDE-Qs adapted

Table 1: Gender participation.

version for adolescence is EDE-A a 36 items self-report measure focuses on past 14 days, accesses the frequency of eating behaviors and aspects of eating psychopathology by scoring four subscales (eating,

weight, shape concerns and restraint). The obtained data was then coded and evaluated by using SPSS version 22. Main aim of the study was to introduce ED to the community, investigate the prevalence and associated risk factors.

RESULTS

The study was carried out in 384 Adolescent students aged between 12-18 years, in them 277 (72%) were females and 107 (28%) were males.

Majority of participants are of age 16 and 12 years 104 (27%) and 95 (25%) respectively. 359 (93.5%) were not suffering from any disease, while only 25 (6.5%) have disease. 171 (44.5%) claims that they know about eating disorders and their risk factors, while 213 (55.5%) have no idea and they were unaware of eating disorders.

Figure 1. Prevalence of eating disorder by Gender.

			Gender		Total	Table
			Male	Female		
Do you know about Eating Disorders?	Yes	Count	35	136	171	2:
		% within Gender	32.7%	49.1%	44.5%	
	No	Count	72	141	213	
		% within Gender	67.3%	50.9%	55.5%	
Total		Count	107	277	384	
		% within Gender	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Knowledge about eating disorders.

According to the SCOFF testing results 236(61.5%) were at risk of developing Eating Disorders out of which 50.5% were male and 65.7% were female. There was a significant association between gender and ED ($p < 0.05$).

Risk of Eating disorder was higher among adolescent with normal BMI which is 16-23 for teens. SCOFF results showed that out of 288 participants with

normal BMI 141(59.7%) were at risk of eating disorder, urban resident (69%), illiterate (41.1%) and high-income group (30.5%) were at risk of developing eating disorders. Participants who were underweight were 75 out of which 30 (12.7%) were prone to risk of eating disorder. For the overweight participants out of 29, 25(10.6%) were at risk of developing eating disorder. It was found that Eating

and Weight concerns were high in females with mean rank of 198.24 and 196.63 respectively. In relation of Risk, Eating Disorder was 0.461($p=0.001$) times higher in females than males and it increased by 0.435($p=0.000$) times in each unit increase of BMI.

DISCUSSION

Our study showed that eating disorder is more prevalent in females than in males, and risk of developing of eating disorder is increased per unit increase in BMI and majority of the population have no idea about eating disorders. While similar results were discussed in another study eating disorders are prevalent among adolescents. Body image perception is considered as a precursor of ED (Schuck et al., 2018). Obesity is considered as a risk factor interconnected with ED triage and body image dissatisfaction it increases the chances by Upto 13 times in adolescence to develop an eating disorder (Cecon et al., 2017). Current study disclosed that Females are more prone to EDs because they get influenced of social environment more and are more concerned about maintain normal BMI and body image. While a study conducted previously tells that most of the adolescents had not been suffering from ED previously but develop Eating Disorders in attempt of losing weight (Golden et al., 2016b). Screening results of is study shows that females are more at a risk of developing eating disorders, and

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more than half of them were unaware of eating disorders. But early detection and family support helps in further physical and psychological complications. Similar findings suggested that screening is important to determine unhealthy eating attitudes. The healthcare workers and policy makers need to focus on nutrition education, risk factors of DEB, mental health and wellbeing and body image concerns (Petisco-Rodríguez et al., 2020). The present study concluded that there is direct link between the BMI and Eating Disorders overweight individuals are at more risk of developing eating disorders because they eagerly want to maintain their normal BMI and body image. Similar study showed that social standards, created by social media or surroundings have direct influence on adolescent especially, girls due to which they adopt various extreme attitudes to attain perfect body(Izydorczyk and Sitnik-Warchulska, 2018).

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1st author have made substantial contributions to the work reported in the manuscript while 2nd and 3rd author help in Writing and data collection.

CONFLICT STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

All authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission.

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